

Clim4**it**is

CLIM4VITIS DAYS - PROCEEDINGS GLOBAL CHANGE IMPACTS ON VITICULTURE - THE LONG WAY FROM SOPHISTICATED EXPERIMENTS AND MODELLING TO PRECISION FARMING

01.-02. DECEMBER 2020
ONLINE

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Document Control Sheet

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1. About the project

Clim4Vitis is a three-year Horizon 2020 project funded by the European Union Research and Innovation programme under the Grant Agreement number 810176. Clim4Vitis finds its framework within the **Twinning instrument** under the all topic: WIDESPREAD-05-2017. It is coordinated by Universidade de Trás-os-Montes e Alto Douro (UTAD) (Portugal), with the support of Potsdam-Institut für Klimafolgenforschung (PIK) (Germany), Università degli studi di Firenze (UNIFI) (Italy), Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST) (Luxembourg) and Sociedade Portuguesa de Inovação (SPI) (Portugal).

Clim4Vitis's main **objective is to strengthen and raise UTAD's science and technology (S&T) capacity and performance** in two main specific fields of research in viticulture & climate:

- Grapevine modelling and
- Methods and tools for assessing climate change impacts on European viticulture.

These objectives will be accomplished by means of various capacity building actions presented in Figure 1.

• **Figure 1: Capacity building actions planned for the Clim4Vitis project.**

2. About the event

The **Clim4Vits days** is the annual main event anticipated within the Clim4Vitis project. The fourth Clim4Vitis days were held on the 1st and 2nd December 2020 and consisted of three capacity building actions: a Thematic Workshop and a Staff Exchange combined with an Expert Webinar. The **Thematic Workshop** was planned under the title:

Global Change Impacts on Viticulture

The long Way from Sophisticated Experiments and Modelling to Precision Farming,

focussing on the suitable adaptation and mitigation measures to lower the impacts of climate change on the viticulture sector, building a communication bridge between scientific research and winegrowers. Therefore, presentations and panel discussions of researchers and important actors of the winegrowing sector were realized, initiating a stronger interaction between science and praxis. The Thematic Workshop features language interpretation for German and English speakers to incorporate also native German speakers into the discussion. The event has in total 57 registered participants.

The **Staff Exchange** and **Expert Webinar** event was intended as an scientific exchange between the Clim4Vitis team and experts of the Hochschule Geisenheim University (HGU). The presentation featured recent results from scientific experiments, numerical modeling and novel tools applied in viticulture.

Due to the COVID-19 pandemic both events of the Clim4Vitis days were held online.

3. Thematic Workshop - Agenda

3.1. Dissemination Flyer

Clim4Vitis
Climate change impact mitigation
for European viticulture

1 December 2020 Via Colibri/Zoom

CLIM4VITIS ONLINE WORKSHOP
Global Change Impacts on Viticulture: The long Way from
Sophisticated Experiments and Modelling to Precision Farming

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AIM OF THE WORKSHOP

This workshop will focus on climate change impacts on viticulture. The different communications will cover topics on climate change adaptation, emerging wine regions and new perspectives in viticulture and winemaking, giving particular emphasis to German wine regions. After each presentation, the audience will be engaged on the topics presented.

The workshop will have German-English / English-German simultaneous translation.

Target audience: Researchers, viticulturists and stakeholders from the winemaking sector, MSc and PhD students.

AGENDA

9:30 – 10:00	Opening Session
10:00 – 11:00	Climate Change and Viticulture (Scientific Introduction)
11:00 – 11:30	Coffee Break
11:30 – 12:30	Emerging viticulture in northern Germany (Traditional and upcoming viticultural areas)
12:30 – 14:00	Lunch Break
14:00 – 15:00	Viticulture in Southern Germany (Quality Wine Making)
15:00 – 15:30	Coffee Break
15:30 – 16:45	Transformation of winemaking (Ecological Winemaking and Ongoing Research)
16:45 – 17:00	Closing

JOIN US!
Participation at the event is free of charge, but registration is compulsory.
<https://eveeno.com/Clim4Vitis-conference>

More info:
<https://eveeno.com/Clim4Vitis-conference>
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3.2. Program Overview

Thematic Workshop	Begin	End	Program	Presenter Topic	Duration
Tuesday, 1 December 2020					
	08:30	09:00	Opening of the zoom portal	Benjamin Kriemann (PIK)	
Welcome & Introduction	09:00	09:10	Opening session	Benjamin Kriemann - Technical Issues	
	09:10	09:20		Hermann Lotze-Campen (PIK) - Welcome	
	09:20	09:40		Hermann Lotze-Campen - Challenge Climate Change	
	09:40	10:00		João dos Santos (UTAD) - Introduction to Clim4Vitis Project	01:00
Session I	10:00	10:20	Climate Change and Viticulture	Christoph Menz (PIK) - Climate Change -The German Wine-growing Regions	
Chair	10:20	10:40	<i>Scientific Introduction</i>	Manfred Stoll (HGU) - Climate Change - Challenges and Adaptation in Viticulture	
L. T. Dirnis	10:40	11:00		Annette Reineke (HGU) - Climate Change - Crop protection	
S. Bernardo			(each: 10min Presentation and 10min Discussion)		01:00
	11:00	11:30	Coffee Break		00:30
Session II	11:30		Emerging Viticulture in Northern Germany	Klaus Schneider (DWW) - Introduction	
Chair			<i>Traditional and Upcoming Viticultural Areas</i>	Thomas Kartschall (PIK) - Simulation results for the Rheingau, Brandenburg and Sylt Regions	
K. Schneider				Manfred Lindicke (Werderaner Wachtelberg Werder/H.) - At the polar circle of viticulture	
Ch. Menz	12:30		(Presentation max. 10min; afterwards Panel Disc.)	Christian Ress (Weingut Balhasar Ress, Eltville-Hattenheim & Sylt) - The Sylt project	01:00
	12:30	14:00	Lunch Break		01:30
Session III	14:00		Viticulture in Southern Germany	Steffen Christmann (VDP) - Introduction	
Chair			<i>Quality Wine Making</i>	Michel Städter (Weingut Schloss Johannisberg)	
S. Christmann				Dieter Greiner (Staatsweingut Kloster Eberbach)	
A.S. Roemer	15:00		(Presentation max. 10min; afterwards Panel Disc.)	Theresa Breuer (Weingut Georg Breuer, Rüdesheim)	01:00
	15:00	15:30	Coffee Break		00:30
Session IV	15:30	15:50	Transformation of Wine Making	Ralph Dejas (EcoVin) - Introduction	
Chair	15:50	16:10	<i>Ecological Viticulture and Ongoing Research</i>	Ilona Leyer (HGU) - BioQuis	
R. Dejas	16:10	16:30		Eckhard Jedicke (HGU) - KiJA-Net	
L. Leolini	16:30	16:50	(each: 10min Presentation and 10min Discussion)	Simone Loose (HGU) - Business Report on Climate Change	01:15
Closing	16:50	17:00	Closing Remarks	Hans Rainer Schultz (HGU)	

3.3. Abstracts

Willkommen & Herausforderung Klimawandel

Hermann Lotze-Campen

*Forschungsabteilung Klimaresilienz, Potsdam-Institut für Klimafolgenforschung
e.V., Telegrafenberg A 31, DE-14473 Potsdam, Deutschland*

Abstract

Der Klimawandel ist bereits sichtbar und schreitet weiter voran. Bislang ist kaum eine Verlangsamung des Trends der ansteigenden Treibhausgas-Emissionen erkennbar. Einzelne Jahre in der jüngeren Vergangenheit, wie der Sommer 2018, geben uns einen Vorgeschmack auf klimatische Verhältnisse, wie wir sie bei ungebremstem Klimawandel in der Zukunft regelmäßig zu erwarten haben. In Paris 2015 wurden ambitionierte Ziele zur Emissionsminderung vereinbart, um die globale Erwärmung auf unter 2 Grad zu begrenzen. Selbst wenn die dafür notwendigen Maßnahmen in den nächsten Jahren zügig umgesetzt werden, muss sich die Agrar- und Ernährungswirtschaft an bereits nicht mehr vermeidbare Klimafolgen anpassen. Gerade für Dauerkulturen ist es notwendig, vorausschauend in Form von angepasster Züchtung und neuen Produktionsverfahren zu reagieren. Andererseits muss auch der Agrar- und Ernährungssektor zur Emissionsminderung beitragen. Stickstoff-Überschüsse und Lachgas-Emissionen müssen verringert werden sowie auch Methan- und CO₂-Emissionen. Es besteht die große Herausforderung, möglichst zügig klimaresiliente, emissionsarme und kohlenstoffoptimierte Produktionsverfahren und Fruchtfolgen zu entwickeln. Nur so kann der Agrar- und Ernährungssektor einen wirksamen Beitrag zu einer nachhaltigen Entwicklung leisten.

Introduction to the Clim4Vitis project

João Carlos Andrade dos Santos

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Abstract

Clim4Vitis is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA), funded by the European Commission under the Twinning instrument of the Horizon 2020 Programme (Grant Agreement 810176). The main objective of Clim4Vitis is to strengthen capacity and performance of the consortium in two main specific fields of research in viticulture & climate: (1) Grapevine modelling; and (2) Methods and tools for assessing climate change impacts on European viticulture, in general, and on grapevine productivity, quality attributes and risk of diseases and pests in particular. The consortium comprises the following partners: Universidade de Trás-os-Montes e Alto Douro (UTAD) – coordinator; Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK); Università degli studi di Firenze (UNIFI); Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology (LIST); and Sociedade Portuguesa de Inovação (SPI). Knowledge transfer and capacity building activities have been organised with the Clim4Vitis framework, engaging students, scientists, technicians, and stakeholders from the European winemaking sector. For more information, please visit our project website on <https://clim4vitis.eu/>.

Climate Change -The European Viticulture Regio

Christoph Menz

*Forschungsabteilung Klimaresilienz, Potsdam-Institut für Klimafolgenforschung
e.V., Telegrafenberg A 31, DE-14473 Potsdam, Deutschland*

Abstract

Der Klimawandel stellt für die deutschen Weinbauregionen eine wesentliche Herausforderung aber auch eine große Chance dar. Die erwartete Erwärmung führt einerseits zur Erschließung neuer Gebiete nördlich der traditionellen Weinbauregionen. Die Zunahme an extremen Hitze- und Trockenereignissen resultiert jedoch andererseits in einen hohen Anpassungsdruck für Anbauggebiete im Süden Deutschlands. Detaillierte Kenntnisse über den Einfluss des Klimawandels in Deutschland sind notwendig, um optimale Anpassungsmaßnahmen zu entwickeln und sicher und nachhaltig für die Zukunft zu planen. Als Einführung in dieses Problemfeld werden daher im Rahmen dieses Vortrags die Ergebnisse der neuesten regionalen Klimaprojektionen für Deutschland vorgestellt. Dabei soll spezielle auf Sorgen und Bedürfnisse des deutschen Weinbaus eingegangen werden.

Climate Change – Challenges for grape crop protection

Annette Reineke

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Abstract

It is broadly accepted that climate change is associated with an increase in overall temperatures as well as an increase in occurrence of extreme events like heat-waves or heavy precipitation. These abiotic factors influence both physiology of grapevines as well as their associated organisms like fungal pathogens and insect pests. Case studies of grapevine pest and diseases and the influence of changed climatic conditions on grapevine-pest-interactions will illustrate the challenges for future pest management strategies in viticulture.

**Simulationsergebnisse zu den Auswirkungen des Klimawandels im
Weinbau Deutschlands mit dem Rebphänologie- und
Traubenwicklermodell
PhenologyVvMoth**

Thomas Kartschall

*Forschungsabteilung Klimaresilienz, Potsdam-Institut für Klimafolgenforschung
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Abstract

Nach einer kurzen Vorstellung der Modellstruktur sowie der wichtigsten Ein- und Ausgabegrößen wurden flächendeckende Simulationen zu Veränderungen der phänologischen Entwicklung und des Spätfrosttrisikos für die Sorte Riesling seit dem Jahre 1930 bis zum Jahre 2018 sowie Abschätzungen bis zum Jahre 2060 vorgestellt. Für die Standorte der am Clim4Vitis Tag mit Vorträgen teilnehmenden Winzer wurden detaillierte Studien der Phänologie und von Spätfrostereignissen i.o.g. Zeitraum durchgeführt.

Folgende allgemeine Aussagen wurden basierend auf den Simulationsergebnissen abgeleitet:

- Der Klimaandel hat mittlerweile deutliche Auswirkungen für den Weinbau Deutschlands.
- Dynamische Modelle eignen sich, die dabei auftretenden komplexen Fragestellungen zu untersuchen.
- Im Einzelnen wurde festgestellt:
- Flächendeckende Beschleunigung/Verfrühung der phänologischen Entwicklung
- Trend einer nord- und ostwärts gerichteten Ausdehnung potenziell geeigneter Anbaubereiche, wobei die regionale Unterschiede bestehen bleiben.

- Das Spätfrostrisiko im Frühjahr hat bisher kaum abgenommen, teilweise traten/treten zwischenzeitliche Zunahmen auf, da Austrieb immer zeitiger erfolgt.
- Die Reifung läuft immer zeitiger und in wärmer werdenden Jahreszeiten ab, was in Zukunft zu Qualitätsproblemen führen kann.

Als Trend für die nächsten Jahrzehnte läßt sich ableiten:

- Die weitere Entwicklung hängt von stark von den eintretenden Emmissionsszenarien ab.
- Im äußersten Norden Deutschlands bleibt Weinbau noch auf Jahre hin problematisch.
- Die im Osten zunehmend aufgerebten Flächen bieten in der Hauptvegetationsperiode zunehmend vergleichbare Bedingungen mit den nördlichen traditionellen Qualitätsanbaugebieten in den 1990er Jahren. Dabei treten durch den tendenziell stärkeren Kontinentaleinfluß nach wie vor höhere Risiken für Frostschäden auf.

Organic Viticulture and its benefit for biodiversity

Ralph Dejas

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Abstract

The climate crisis and biodiversity crisis must also be actively addressed to the wine industry. The ECOVIN Biodiversity Action Plan provides more than 100 possible adjusting possibilities for this.

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) is a platform that the World Association of Meteorologists and the United Nations founded in 1988. According to the current (fifth) assessment report (2013), the climatic conditions in large parts of the world will change even faster and more dramatically than previously assumed. This will lead to major changes in the wine industry, which will affect adaptation strategies, water management, variety selection and biodiversity.

The advancement of Europe's wine-growing regions to the north is an effect of climate change. In Denmark and Sweden, for example, viticulture is practiced today. In Germany, the Merlot grape variety is no longer exotic. The few advantages of climate change for viticulture (more hours of sunshine, more CO₂ content, higher grape ripeness and more aroma / color formation) contrasts with a significantly longer negative list.

The loss of biodiversity is a major negative factor here. In addition to the climate crisis, the biodiversity crisis is at least as challenging. Political decision-makers are now also aware of this problem. The European Green Deal, with its ambitious goal of reducing greenhouse gas emissions to zero by 2050 and thus becoming the first continent to become climate-neutral, or the European Union's Farm to Fork Strategy will hopefully also contribute achieving the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDG).

In 2019, ECOVIN, the Federal Association of Organic Viticulture in Germany, integrated the Biodiversity Action Plan (BAP) into its guideline. In his lecture, Ralph Dejas shows selected examples to demonstrate which adjusting possibilities have been identified in the wine industry to decrease the biodiversity crisis.

KliA-Net: Kooperationen zur Klimaanpassung im Weinbau am Beispiel des Rheingaus

Eckhard Jedicke

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Abstract

Vorge stellt wird ein Projekt zur Netzw erkbildung von Kooperationen zur Klimaanpassung in Weinbau-Landschaften am Beispiel des Rheingaus – KliA-Net_Weinbau. Darin werden zukunftsorientierte Handlungs- und Umsetzungskonzepte ermöglicht, mit deren Hilfe regionale Akteure aus Kommunen, Betrieben, Verbänden, Fachbehörden und der Wissenschaft gemeinsam auf die klimatischen Veränderungen im Weinbau ökologisch und ökonomisch effektiv reagieren können, maßgeblich begründet durch das Konzept der Ökosystemleistungen. KliA-Net_Weinbau schafft hierbei die Möglichkeit zu einem Wissenstransfer zwischen der wissenschaftlichen Forschung und der weinbaulichen Praxis.

Business Record Climate Change

Simone Loose

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Abstract

In 2019 Geisenheim University surveyed more than 1,700 experts in the wine industry from 45 countries. The survey focused on the effects of climate change on the global wine industry. The study covers the complete value chain of wine. Climate change confronts the sector with major challenges which have already been felt by actors over the past five years. Grape and wine producers have so far been and will also continue to be hardest hit by climate change. They often only have few alternatives since they are tied to their vineyards in most cases. Through changes in viticultural practices, in harvest management, in oenological practices as well as through the use of irrigation the effects of climate change on grapes and wine are mitigated. For the future, it is anticipated that new grape varieties more tolerant to heat and drought stress will be in great demand. Beyond these adaptation measures in existing wine-growing regions wine growing will increasingly shift to cooler growing regions in higher altitudes or further away from the equator.

4. Staff Exchange and Expert Webinar – Agenda

4.1. Program Overview

Staff Exchange	Begin	End	Topic	Presenter	Duration
Wednesday 2020-12-02					
	08:50	09:00	Opening of the zoom portal	Christoph Menz & Thomas Kartschall (PIK)	00:10
Session I Experiments at HGU	09:00	09:30	Introduction and General Overview	Manfred Stoll (HGU)	
	09:30	10:00	VitVoltaic: a new approach in sustainability	Claudia Kammann (HGU)	
	10:00	10:20	Water balance model	Marco Hofmann (HGU)	
	10:20	10:40	Advancing viticultural research with digital tools	Matthias Friedel (HGU)	
	10:40	11:00	A virtual German Riesling	Katrin Kahlen & Dominik Maria Schmidt (HGU)	01:30
	11:00	11:30	Coffee Break		00:30
Session II-a Modeling Reports	11:30	12:00	Bias Adjustment of Climate Models for Viticulture	Christoph Menz (PIK)	
	12:00	12:30	PhenologyVVMoth	Thomas Kartschall (PIK)	01:00
	12:30	14:00	Lunch Break		01:30
Session II-b Modeling Reports	14:00	14:30	Climate Change and Grapevine Modelling	Luisa Leolini (Unifl)	
	14:30	15:00	Phenology and Disease Models for grapevine cultivars in Luxembourg: scalable implementations	Arturo Torres (LIST)	
	15:00	15:30	Simultaneous calibration of grapevine phenology and yield with a soil-crop system model using a frequentist method	Chenyao Yang (UTAD)	01:30

4.2. Abstracts

Bias Adjustmen of Climate Models for Viticulture

Christoph Menz

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Abstract

Global and regional climate model projections are frequently used to drive various kinds of climate change impact models. However, climate models still exhibit large systematic biases, rendering the simulations impractical for most impact studies. Therefore, various statistical methods were developed to remove these biases. These methods are called bias adjustment methods. Bias adjustment of global and regional climate models has gained significant attraction in the past 15 years and have been applied in various climate change impact studies.

Different bias adjustment methods were developed showing an increasing sophistication from simple methods adjusting single statistical properties of one variable, to distribution adjustments and multi-variable adjustments. Different impact models have different requirements for the quality of the bias adjusted climate models with which they are driven. Therefore, the variety of methods motivates the user need for a bias adjustment method inter-comparison to help choosing a method for a specific application. Bias model inter-comparisons were recently done within the hydrology or crop modeling communities. However, there exist no such comparison for grapevine phenology models.

Here we present the first bias model inter-comparison focusing on grapevine phenology modeling. Due to the specific requirements of those models, we focus our comparison on the performance of the methods to adjust the tails of the temperature distribution. Particular focus is given to the adjustment of frost and heat events relevant for the phenological development of grapevine. Furthermore, we validated the models using simple phenological models like the Huglin and Winkler index.

Förderung der Biodiversität und Ökosystemleistungen durch Querterrassierung im Steillagenweinbau – BioQuiS

Ilona Leyer

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Abstract

Der Weinbau ist in den Steillagen Deutschlands im Rückgang begriffen, weil vielerorts die wirtschaftliche Tragfähigkeit der überwiegend in Falllinie angelegten Weinberge nicht mehr gegeben ist. Eine Alternative ist die Querterrassierung, die neben einer vereinfachten Bewirtschaftung ein großes Potenzial der Biodiversitätsförderung mit sich bringt. Im Rahmen des Projektes BioQuiS wurden Querterrassenweinberge neu angelegt. Eine Begrünungsstudie ermittelt die Möglichkeiten der Etablierung artenreicher Böschungsvegetation im Kontext klimatischer Veränderungen. Ferner werden etablierte Falllinien- versus Querterrassenweinberge vergleichend im Hinblick z.B. auf Unterschiede in der Diversität verschiedener Artengruppen und auf weinbauliche und mikroklimatische Aspekte analysiert. Einige Ergebnisse zu diesen Studien werden vorgestellt.

VitiVoltaic4Future: An new approach to use climate mitigation tools as adaptation strategies in viticulture

Claudia Kammann

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Abstract

Rising temperatures and persistent heat waves have demonstrated over the last summers that the future of traditional grapevine varieties demands continuous adaptation of viticultural practices. Within VitiVoltaic4Future, we aim to set up a vineyard agro-photovoltaic real lab for R&D. The aim is to combine green energy production with the adaptation of viticultural production to global warming and with the pro-active development of innovative technical (digital, autonomous) technical solutions.

Clim4^uitis